

Do we, as educators, have to be neutral in our classroom?

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Abstract

Using controversial issues in classroom can provide interesting learning opportunities. Having to face such situations can make students being aware about how technical decisions can be biased by underlying personal values.

In this hands-on session attendees will face the question about the convenience, or not, of maintaining neutrality in front of our students when including values and ethics in engineering.

Keywords: Politics and Education; Ethics and Values in Engineering Education; Promoting Global Awareness.

1 Introduction

The underlying idea of this hands-on session is well described by the topic of the conference, planting the seed: *promoting engineers with global awareness*, which can be understood as a statement of intent. If we take a picture of the global situation, this global awareness we try to seed in our students implies much more than technical contents.

If we are aware of the social implications of engineering, any decision-making process can be extremely complicated. As stated in the call for papers, *'What we do as engineers and why we do it, is based on our underlying values. However, rarely in engineering education is any consideration taken of our values, what they are and where they come from'* (Nahar and Baillie, 2009). In this sense, when introducing ethics in engineering in our courses we need to understand how our own values are affecting our decisions. From what perspective should we approach this issue?

In the session attendees will face the question about the convenience, or not, of maintaining neutrality in front of our students when including values and ethics in engineering.

This is, without doubt, a controversial topic. Making a fast search on the Internet, you can find teaching professionals with three main points of view, against neutrality, pro neutrality or making it content dependant (left, right and mid sections in figure 1). In short, the answers would be 'yes', 'no' or 'it depends'.

Figure 1. Screenshot of some Internet posts reflecting the three main positions about the topic.

The session will be organized (among others) around the following questions:

- Is neutrality the most polite position?
- Can (or must) we share our political position in the classroom?
- Can we include ethics and values from a neutral position?

- Do we have to show a political position based on the values of our institution?
- Can role-play be an instrument to include political positions without making it personal?
- How to consider the effect of individual personality (introvert - extrovert)?
- What will happen with students not aligned with our opinion?

2 Activities

The main tasks will be performed in small groups. The session will be organized as follows:

- Topic presentation.
- Warm-up activity.
- Group activities (debates / role-play).
- Discussion.
- Conclusion.

3 Expected results

As the session topic does not have an answer, we will try to explore our own starting position and see if it changes or not at the end. We will be expecting to have enriching debates.

4 References

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